

Romatolojik Hastalıklarda Kognitif Disfonksiyonlar

Cognitive Dysfunctions In Rheumatological Diseases

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Öz:

Amaç: Bu derleme çalışması, romatolojik hastalıklarda kognitif disfonksiyonları ve nedenlerini hastalıklara spesifik olarak incelemektedir. Romatolojik hastalıklar kapsamında, romatoid artrit, spondiloartrit, sistemik lupus eritematozus, sistemik skleroz, primer sjögren sendromu, fibromiyalji, primer sistemik vaskülitler ve behçet hastalığı ele alınmıştır. **Yöntem:** Mevcut literatür araştırmaları sentezlendiğinde, kronik inflamasyonun merkezi sinir sisteminde nöroinflamatuvar strese yol açarak, günlük kognisyonla ilişkili aktivitelerin tamamlanmasında ek kortikal kaynakların kullanılmasına neden olabileceğine dikkat çekilmektedir. Ayrıca, beyin bölgelerinin, ağrı ile olan meşguliyetleri nedeniyle kognitif görevlerini yerine getiremediklerinden dolayı kognitif disfonksiyonun meydana gelebileceği vurgulanmaktadır. **Sonuçlar:** Romatizmal hastalıklarda bilişsel bozulmaya katkıda bulunan faktörlerin hastalık türüne bağlı olabileceği bir diğer bulgudur. Romatoid Artrit’li çoğu hasta, inflamasyon arttıkça izole kognitif görevleri sağlıklı bireylerle aynı düzeyde gerçekleştirebilmek için, daha fazla serebral korteks bölgesi kullanmaktadır. Lupus’ta kognitif disfonksiyonun altında yatan yollar hala araştırılmaktadır ve parametreler henüz tam olarak doğrulanıp geniş çapta kabul edilmemiştir. Sistemik Skleroz’lu hastalarda soğuğa maruz kalmanın zihinsel veya bilişsel etkilerine ilişkin çeşitli raporlar mevcuttur. Primer Sjögren Sendromu’nda sınırlı kanıtlar hipoperfüzyonun kognitif işlev bozukluğuyla ilişkili olabileceğini göstermektedir. Fibromiyalji’de ağrı derecesinin kognitif disfonksiyon düzeyi ile direkt ilişki olduğu ortak görüştür. Primer Sistemik Vaskülitler’de serebral hipoperfüzyon nedeniyle kognitif fonksiyonlarda etkilenim olabilir. Behçet hastalığında kognitif disfonksiyon yaş, anksiyete-depresif bozukluklar, kronik stres etkenleri ve minör beyin multifokal subkortikal parankimal MRG lezyonları ile ilişkilidirler.

Tartışma: Sonuç olarak, romatolojik hastalıklarda hastalığa spesifik bazı faktörler kognitif disfonksiyona neden olabilmektedir. Ancak, kafa karıştırıcı faktörlerin varlığı ve güvenilir biyobelirteçlerin eksikliği nedeniyle klinik kullanım sınırlıdır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Ağrı, İnflamasyon, Kognitif Disfonksiyon, Romatolojik Hastalık

Abstract

Aim: This review examines cognitive dysfunctions and their causes in rheumatological diseases on a disease-specific basis. The rheumatological diseases include rheumatoid arthritis, spondyloarthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic sclerosis, primary sjögren syndrome, fibromyalgia, primary systemic vasculitis, and behçet's disease. **Method:** A synthesis of existing literature highlights that chronic inflammation can lead to neuroinflammatory stress in the central nervous system, requiring the use of additional cortical resources to complete daily cognition-related activities. It also emphasizes that cognitive dysfunction may occur because brain regions are unable to perform cognitive tasks due to their preoccupation with pain. **Results:** Another finding is that the factors contributing to cognitive impairment in rheumatic diseases may depend on the type of disease. Many patients with rheumatoid arthritis use more cerebral cortex areas to perform isolated cognitive tasks at the same level as healthy individuals as inflammation increases. The pathways underlying cognitive dysfunction in Lupus are still being investigated, and the parameters have not yet been fully validated and widely accepted. In patients with Systemic Sclerosis, there are various reports on the mental or cognitive effects of exposure to cold. Limited evidence in Primary Sjogren's Syndrome suggests that hypoperfusion may be associated with cognitive dysfunction. In Fibromyalgia, it is commonly believed that the degree of pain is

directly related to the level of cognitive dysfunction. Cognitive function may be affected due to cerebral hypoperfusion in primary systemic vasculitis. In Behçet's disease, cognitive dysfunction is associated with age, anxiety-depressive disorders, chronic stress factors, and minor brain multifocal subcortical parenchymal MRI lesions. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, some disease-specific factors may cause cognitive dysfunction in rheumatological diseases. However, their clinical utility is limited due to the presence of confounding factors and the lack of reliable biomarkers.

Key Words: Cognitive Dysfunction, Inflammation, Pain, Rheumatic Disease

1.Introduction

Cognitive function includes attention/concentration, orientation, verbal, visual/spatial judgment/problem solving and memory, and executive functions. The cognitive domains most frequently affected in rheumatic diseases are visuospatial perception, executive functions, memory, and attention. More than 90% of individuals with rheumatic diseases experience attention and memory problems (1,2). Cognitive dysfunctions are most strongly associated with depression among demographic factors (advanced age and low educational level), health-related risk factors including obesity, chronic pain, disease activity, and psychological factors (3-5).

Inflammation: In the last approximately five years, especially with developments in the context of functional neuroimaging, the effects of inflammation and immunomodulation on the central nervous system and cognition have been attempted to be explained (6). Many rheumatic diseases are characterized by inflammatory activity. Although inflammation is not the primary cause of the pathology of each condition, it is known to make significant contributions to the primary disease indicators (7,8). The brain and the immune system are actually in constant bidirectional communication and coordinated activity. When the activation of the peripheral immune system continues without reduction in inflammatory rheumatic diseases, the immune signal to the brain can lead to disease flares and more severe symptoms in vulnerable individuals. Very little is known about the mechanisms of immune cells in the brain, the contribution of pro-

inflammatory cytokine signals to activation, and their relationship with cognitive functions (9). It is suggested that cognitive dysfunctions can occur without neurological deficits. There is no clear consensus on which neurobiological mechanisms are involved (10). One hypothesis is that in some patients, chronic inflammation leads to neuroinflammatory stress in the central nervous system, causing the use of additional cortical resources to complete activities related to daily cognition (11). The inflammatory mediators used to monitor disease activity do not clearly demonstrate the inflammatory signaling in the central nervous system. As we investigate biomarkers that better reflect the inflammatory sensitivity of the central nervous system, it may become possible to simultaneously monitor different aspects of the inflammatory response in rheumatic diseases (12). In rheumatic diseases, due to the complexity of each disease and the great variability in symptoms, it is believed that the effects of inflammation on the central nervous system and the mechanisms involved will branch out in many directions with a better understanding (6).

Chronic Pain: Cognitive dysfunction is a particularly severe comorbidity of chronic pain. Clinical evidence shows that approximately 20% of individuals with chronic pain experience cognitive impairment (13). It has been noted that these individuals have a higher risk of dementia and experience faster cognitive decline (14). Chronic pain can disrupt normal cognitive processes, leading to impairments in learning and memory, attention, and cognitive flexibility (15). Clinical research has shown that individuals with chronic pain often struggle with tasks requiring sustained attention and that chronic pain may cause permanent changes in neurobiological attention mechanisms (16). Cognitive flexibility is an executive function primarily controlled by the PFC. One hypothesis regarding the comorbidity of chronic pain and cognitive impairment is that many brain regions involved in cognitive function partially overlap with regions that play a key role in pain perception and control (referred to as the "pain matrix"). This overlap suggests that cognitive dysfunction arises because these brain regions cannot perform their cognitive tasks due to their focus on pain. Neuroimaging studies have shown that the chronicity of pain occurs alongside

a shift in brain activity from sensory structures to emotional and limbic structures (17). Structural and functional plasticity changes in corticolimbic regions (prefrontal cortex (PFC), anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), hippocampus, and amygdala) contribute to the development of chronic pain (18). Changes in these regions during chronic pain can also disrupt cognitive processing.

2. Rheumatoid Arthritis

The causes of cognitive dysfunction in Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) include the following:

- Inflammation itself, which also affects the brain, and accelerated atherosclerosis caused by systemic inflammation, including pro-inflammatory cytokines.
- Disease activity associated with systemic inflammation.
- Among anti-rheumatic drugs, methotrexate (MTX) and corticosteroids have been associated with cognitive dysfunction. However, the results are controversial. Some studies indicate that both MTX and corticosteroids reduce systemic inflammation and therefore may be beneficial for cognitive functions. On the other hand, MTX has been associated with cognitive dysfunction, mood changes, and confusion, while corticosteroids are highlighted for their potential effects on memory and hippocampal function.
- Clinical features such as pain, stress, fatigue, and sleep disorders are also among the causes of cognitive dysfunction. For example, depression can lead to abnormal concentration and executive functions (19,20).

In most patients with RA, as inflammation increases, more cerebral cortex areas are required to perform isolated cognitive tasks at the same level as healthy individuals (11). Additionally, task-focused studies have shown that chronic pain affects dual tasks that require the use of complex cognitive functions (executive functions), rather than simple tasks (21).

3. Spondyloarthritis

Recent studies have shown that spondyloarthritis (SpA) can affect the brain, in addition to symptoms affecting the joints, skin, eyes, and gastrointestinal

system. Magnetic resonance imaging analyses have identified changes in brain structure and function in these patients (22). While current evidence provides limited information about cognitive function in SpA, it suggests that dementia rates are increased in patients with psoriatic arthritis (PsA) and ankylosing spondylitis (AS), and that cognitive impairment is more prevalent in SpA patients than in non-rheumatic control groups (23,24). 20.6% of PsA patients and 23.6% of AS patients complained of cognitive burden, including intellectual impairments in areas such as memory, speech, and concentration (25,26). Compared to healthy controls, AS patients have been found to have significantly lower mean scores on verbal fluency, the clock drawing test, and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), and this has been associated with poor functioning (23). Lower MoCA scores have also been found in PsA patients compared to healthy individuals, and this has been reported to be related to disease duration, age, fatigue, quality of life, and poor physical condition (24). Cognitive impairment in SpA is thought to be more severe than currently available data suggest (27).

4. Systemic Lupus Erythematosus

In systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), up to 90% of patients experience some concurrent neuropsychiatric symptoms, while cognitive dysfunction affects 3-81% of SLE patients. Although often considered vague and non-specific, lupus patients have described cognitive dysfunction as one of the most distressing symptoms of their disease (28).

Neuropsychiatric symptoms in SLE appear at an early stage. In 40% of lupus patients, neuropsychiatric symptoms are observed at the time of presentation or within the first three years following the diagnosis (29). There is increasing awareness that cognitive dysfunction in lupus patients is not adequately diagnosed and addressed in clinical settings (30). Compared to other chronic inflammatory diseases, the higher prevalence of cognitive dysfunction in lupus patients strongly suggests a disease-specific immunological etiology (28). Antiphospholipid (aPL) antibodies, known to be a strong risk factor for neuropsychiatric SLE, are associated with cognitive dysfunction. Neurotoxic/psychoactive drugs such as corticosteroids and

cyclophosphamide are indicated as another risk factor. Other neuropsychiatric SLE symptoms, such as depression or anxiety, can independently lead to cognitive dysfunction (31,32). In patients with cognitive dysfunction in SLE, the following results have been obtained:

- Entry of systemic autoimmune drivers into the central nervous system
- Choroid plexus and blood-brain barrier abnormalities
- Specifically, various studies have shown increases in systemic cytokine levels such as interleukin 6 (IL-6) and anti-N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR) antibodies
- Type I interferon and anti-NMDAR antibodies have been shown to increase microglial activation and subsequent abnormal synaptic pruning with CD (33,34). The pathways underlying lupus cognitive dysfunction are still under investigation, and the parameters have not yet been fully validated and widely accepted.

5. Systemic Sclerosis

Although anxiety, depression, and mood problems are common, cognitive dysfunction in Systemic Sclerosis (SSc) is not a frequently seen complication of the disease process. SSc rarely directly affects brain functions (35). Evidence of cognitive dysfunction has been found in SSc patients compared to healthy individuals, and the Medsger severity vascular score has been reported to be closely associated with cognitive impairment. Future studies may investigate whether this is related to comorbidities (such as depression, social impact) or is a specific feature of SSc (36). It is noteworthy that SSc is associated with Raynaud's phenomenon, and there are various reports regarding the mental or cognitive effects of exposure to cold. This has been linked to changes in cerebral perfusion scans in some cases, suggesting an intriguing possibility that Raynaud's could occasionally affect cerebral circulation. However, this has not been conclusively demonstrated, and further research is needed (37).

6. Primary Sjögren's Syndrome

The underlying pathogenic mechanisms in Primary Sjögren's Syndrome (pSS) are largely

unknown, but limited evidence suggests that hypoperfusion may be associated with cognitive dysfunction, suggesting microvasculopathy as a potential pathogenetic mechanism (38). A systematic review reported insufficient studies on cognitive function in pSS, often conducted on small sample sizes and frequently contradictory (39). In a study by Goulabchand et al. (2022), 53% of pSS patients exhibited a pathological cognitive profile. Cognitive impairments in pSS cannot be solely explained by anxiety, depression, or sleep disorders. Future studies requiring comprehensive cognitive assessment and possibly biomarkers or specific brain imaging (assessing functional connectivity and microstructural changes in the brain) are needed (40).

7. Fibromyalgia

Cognitive dysfunction observed in Fibromyalgia (FM) is now increasingly recognized as a distinct clinical condition. FM patients not only rate their cognitive performance worse compared to healthy controls but also significantly worse compared to individuals with other rheumatic diseases or chronic pain problems (41). Nearly half of FM patients score the severity of these symptoms on a scale ranging from 0 to 10, rating it ≥ 6 (42). It is commonly held that the degree of pain is directly related to the level of cognitive dysfunction (43). Studies examining the relationship between cognitive dysfunction and depression or depressive symptoms in FM have varied in their findings: some fully explain this relationship, some partially clarify it, and others show no relationship at all. FM patients with cognitive dysfunction have been found to exhibit lower activity levels in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (17,44). Studies comparing FM patients to healthy individuals have also shown significant decreases in gray matter density in brain areas involved in high-level cognitive processes such as the anterior cingulate cortex, prefrontal cortex, and insular cortex (45,46). Montoro et al. demonstrated in their studies that FM patients use more brain regions to achieve the same level of functionality as healthy controls (43).

8. Primary Systemic Vasculitides

In Primary Systemic Vasculitides, cognitive impairment may occur due to cerebral

hypoperfusion (47). A key finding from a study by Mullin et al. is that patients with vasculitis affecting both the central nervous system and peripheral nervous system experience cognitive dysfunction. However, cognitive dysfunction is significantly more prevalent in central nervous system vasculitis. There is currently no information available regarding the mechanism of cognitive dysfunction (48).

9. Behçet's Disease

In Behçet's disease, inflammation can affect arteries and veins of all sizes. Cognitive dysfunction is a common characteristic of most Behçet's patients. It is associated with age, anxiety-depressive disorders, chronic stress factors, and minor brain multifocal subcortical parenchymal MRI lesions (49). In a study by Urbain et al., cognitive involvement was significantly associated with Behçet's disease activity score but not with brain MRI abnormalities (50).

10. Conclusions

At the basic science level, research on cytokine-mediated cognitive dysfunction is still in its early stages. If it is true that some individuals are more vulnerable to the effects of inflammation on the central nervous system, then we need to understand what contributes to this vulnerability. Factors contributing to cognitive impairment in rheumatic diseases may vary depending on the type of disease. Some factors have been found to contribute to cognitive dysfunction. However, there is weak specificity in distinguishing between symptoms, which limits clinical utility (due to the presence of confusing factors and lack of reliable biomarkers). From a practical perspective, patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases who have ongoing disease activity and higher damage indices should be evaluated for cognitive dysfunction using standard tests. It is clear that there is still much work to be done to develop accurate assessment tools to provide the best service and management for these patients burdened with the additional complication of cognitive dysfunction in already challenging diseases (6,51).

Effective pain and disease management can alleviate cognitive impairment. Reports indicate that successful treatment of chronic pain can partially alleviate the gray matter loss and

cognitive network impairment caused by chronic pain (52). The exercise component of lifestyle medicine and cognitive behavioral therapy may be an effective and clinically important intervention to protect against cognitive dysfunction (53-55).

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